

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B112
Date: 19 Jul 2005
Take Off 08:58:41
Landing: 13:54:52
Flight Time 4h56m11s

Campaign: AMPEP

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Norfolk to S coast, S coast to Firth of Forth via eastern coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	David Fowler	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
6	CCM2/Filters	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	AMS	Keith Bower	Manchester University
9	AMS training	Gerrard Capes	Manchester University
10	Core chem / TDLAS	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	PAN/WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
12	Bags 1	Alan McDonald	CEH
13	Bags 2	Mark Theobald	CEH
14	Ptr-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
15	Ptr-MS training	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
16	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B112 Track 19-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B112
 Date: 19 Jul 2005
 Project: AMPEP
 Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
083844		INU to Nav	0.31 kft	126	
084514		start taxi	0.31 kft	126	
085841		T/O	0.78 kft	268	
090537	092325	Run 1	10.0 kft	099	backgnd & cal
092753	092857	Run 2	6.2 kft	179	
092907	093102	Profile 1	6.2 - 4.2 kft	175	
093102	093209	Run 3	4.2 kft	182	
093209	093406	Profile 2	4.2 - 2.2 kft	200	
093408	093523	Run 4	2.2 kft	188	
093523	093649	Profile 3	2.2 - 0.95 kft	193	
093650	093752	Run 5	0.95 - 0.97 kft	188	
093753	093858	Profile 4	0.97 - 0.46 kft	199	
093858	094006	Run 6	0.46 kft	200	
094006	094042	Profile 5	0.46 - 0.20 kft	196	
094043	094138	Run 7	0.20 - 0.21 kft	196	
094231	100625	Run 8	0.94 - 0.92 kft	198	Radalt 1kft WP43
095204		WP42	0.88 kft	200	
101324	120532	Run 9	0.92 - 1.1 kft	054	
102111		WP42	0.86 kft	026	
103451		WP41	0.90 kft	353	surface P 1016hPa
105300			0.96 kft	308	surface P 1015hPa
105924		WP87	0.99 kft	288	
111508			0.99 kft	325	surface P 1014hPa
112050		WP80	0.99 kft	318	surface P 1012hPa
113904		WP79	1.0 kft	338	surface P 1010 hPa
115530		WP77	1.1 kft	318	
120106		surface 1008 hPa	1.1 kft	319	
120434		WP76	1.1 kft	319	
120859	120944	Run 10	0.45 - 0.48 kft	179	250ft
120945	121007	Profile 6	0.49 - 0.69 kft	165	
121007	121110	Run 11	0.71 - 0.72 kft	162	500ft
121110	121151	Profile 7	0.72 - 1.2 kft	161	
121151	121234	Run 12	1.2 kft	151	1000ft
121234	121343	Profile 8	1.2 - 2.1 kft	146	
121343	121447	Run 13	2.1 kft	154	2000ft
121447	121649	Profile 9	2.1 - 4.1 kft	152	
121650	121743	Run 14	4.1 kft	152	4000ft
121743	121938	Profile 10	4.1 - 6.0 kft	168	
121938	122041	Run 15	6.0 kft	171	6000ft
123757	132500	Run 16	1.0 - 0.99 kft	188	
124303		WP79	1.0 kft	146	
125851		WP80	1.1 kft	162	
130841			1.0 kft	160	surface P 1014hPa
132840	134209	Run 17	10.0 kft	260	cal run
135452		Land	0.30 kft	353	
140335		final GPS posn	0.27 kft	305	52 04.36N 00 37.50W

B112 Track 19-JUL-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B 112

Mission Scientist: David Fowler, CEH

Date 19-July-2005

Outline schedule:

06:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
08:00 – Briefing
09:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
09:30 – Doors close
10:00 – Take off Cranfield
14:50 – Land Cranfield
15:20 – Debrief
18:00 – Power down

Location: East coast transect of the UK, northbound followed by southbound between Dover and the Firth of Forth.

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the country in Westerly airflow over Britain. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass in Westerly airflow over the UK. The low pressure to the North of Scotland limits the area of the UK over which we can work, however the general airflow over the bulk of the country presents the best set of synoptic conditions for AMPEP we have seen to date. In particular the windspeeds and direction are excellent.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the East coast along a Northbound transect beginning off the coast of Norfolk, heading south to Kent, then returning north along the coast to the Firth of Forth. The return is along the same path, turning west for Cranfield from the Norfolk coast. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once stepping down into the sample track south from the Norfolk coast and again at the North end of the transect. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 10:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 40 near East Anglia; background filter run & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+20 Profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 100)
- c) T+35 Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast.
- d) T+160? Off the Firth of Forth profile (100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- e) T+ Heading south from Firth of Forth to Norfolk at 1000ft

- f) T+.... At WP 40 climb to 10000ft to calibrate NO_{xy} during transit to Cranfield
- g) T+ 290 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 – Alan Foster
3. CCM – Sue Angold
4. CCM 2 Steve Devereau
5. Cloud Physics – Martyn Pickering
6. CVI Paul James
7. Flight Manager – Jim Crawford
8. Mission Scientist – David Fowler
9. Core Chemistry/TDLAS/PAN – Ruth Purvis
10. Core Chemistry Training Maureen Smith
11. Filters – Steve Devereau
12. WAS – Maria Nielsdottir
13. Bag Sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
14. Bag Sampling 2 – Mark Theobald
15. AMS – Keith Bower
16. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
17. PTRMS–Training Jennifer Murphy
18. NO_{xy} – Dave Stewart

MAPS:

Cranfield T/O 10:00
40
42
43
42
40
87
80
79
77
76
77
79
80
87
40
Cranfield land.14:50

Monday 18 July 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Tuesday 19 July 2005 12UTC
Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO_3 & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH_3). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S \rightarrow N and N \rightarrow S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO , SO_2 , NO and NO_2 will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NO_{xy}: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO

Take off from Cranfield at 08:58 climbing to 10,000ft and heading East to the Norfolk coast, during which NO_x calibration and background filter and bottles samples were taken during Run 1 beginning 09:05. A series of bag samples were also taken during Run 1. Run 2 beginning 09:28 at 6000ft was the first of the profile steps which continued with 4000ft, 2000ft, 1000ft, 500ft and 250ft. At 09:43, the level sampling run within the boundary layer began, sampling into bags at 1 per minute, and bottles and filters beginning while heading south towards Kent. The sampling continued around the coastline of SE England until the end of the Run at WP 43, a short distance west of Beachy Head. Turning back to the east and sampling at 1000ft, the next phase of the flight began on Run 9. The eastern section of the English Channel was very congested and the shipping in this area may be an important source of the measured primary pollutants.

Sampling continued east to Dover, then north to Ramsgate, and continued North, East of Essex, Suffolk and Norfolk, then off the Lincolnshire coast close to WP 87. Modest concentrations of the primary pollutants, with SO₂ concentrations generally smaller than 1ppb, but with substantial structure in the particle number concentrations. Sampling continued north to the Yorkshire coast, where plumes of SO₂ and NO₂, CO and aerosols were detected. Bag sampling continued at 1 per minute throughout and filter samples were arranged to provide approx 20 minute samples.

Run 9 continued north with clear plumes of the primary gaseous pollutants and aerosols from Teesside and Newcastle. The Run ended at 12:09 in the Firth of Forth and a stepped profile with bag sampling was initiated. The sampling heights were 250ft, 500ft, 1000ft, 2000ft 4000ft and 6000ft. Sampling at 1000ft as Run 16 began at 12:38 east of Durham, in light rain. The flight again crossed plumes of the gaseous and particulate pollutants on the southbound track. Run 16 ended at 13:26 off the Norfolk coast close to Cromer filters also stopped at this point.

Return to Cranfield at 10000ft, with NO_x calibration and further bag sampling. Landed at 13:42.

David Fowler, CEH

Mission Scientist's Log

DAVIS FOREVER

- P. 1000
0800 - 1000
- B. 1000
1300

Flight No **B.112**

Date **19 JULY 05**

Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc).
0815					on board all instruments operating
0845					Altitude point, prep for take-off
0858					Take off SW (200) → 5000 ft NW, NE Climbing to 10,000 ft. Cool - fair + breeze
0905	1	10k			NE. Bkgd. Billies + Kites
0908	1	10k			Bag samples - 0.1g of 3000 ft. Can all be seen
0915	1	10k			10 bag samples - WP 4.0
0919	1	10k	ENE		40 ppb O ₃ 93 ppb CO, 1000 ^{NE} - 2.4
0923	-				End of Run 1. Lower Gr. Yarn
0920					descend to 6000 ft. S, along C.A.S.I.
0928	2	6000	S		6k - bags full
0929	profile 1				descend to 4k over sea & lowland
0931	3	4000	S		at approx top of B.S. 1
0932	profile 2		203		descend to 2500 ft. O ₃ drops 20 ppb Mix pulling up 1-2 ppb
0934	4	2550	2189		Run 4 full. 10000 ft correction
0935	Profile 3	↓			descend to 1k ft O ₃ dropping 5 ppb
0936	5	1000			13 ppb NO _x → 3 ppb NO _x
0937	profile 4				→ 2500
0939	6	500			500 ft O ₃ Suph, Mix 4 ppb!
0940	profile 5				→ 250
0941	7	250			
0942	→ 1000 ft				
0943	8	1000			Bags on final sampling 15 ppb
0946	8	1000			Rainy
0950	8	1000			Dark Sp. 1000 ft, 1000 ft 11 ^{ppb} O ₃ 94 ppb
0952	8	1000			WP 4.2 - 3 NO _x - 5 SO ₂ 9 O ₃ 102 ppb
					huge increase in CPC. CO 97
0950	8	1000			Dangerous PS, 2 ppb NO _x - 5 SO ₂ 10 O ₃

Mission Scientist's Log

David Fowler

Flight No B...112

Date 19 JULY 05

Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc).
10:00	8	1020ft	237		1.4 NO _x , 1.0 SO ₂ , 11 ppb O ₃ , 95 CO, 40R pm ₁₀
10:06	8	1070ft			MANITWAN Engine room pt #13
10:07	—				Beaching Head 10:07 at 8,100ft
10:08	—				Turning back to E at 5000ft O ₃ 51
		5000ft			at 5000ft NO _x - 0.6 SO ₂ - 0.17, O ₃ 30ppb
10:11		5120ft			descend to 1000ft Brn, in air
					pkcs went down: 2 1/2 pm ₁₀ 31k
10:13	9	1000	54°		1.2 NO _x , 0.6 SO ₂ , 10 ppb O ₃ 30
10:17		1000			Huge oil sheeping platform in situ (41)
10:18	9	1000	56°		Dover, 1.4 NO _x , 0.3 SO ₂ , 11 O ₃ , 95 CO 32k
10:20	9	1000			WP42 Dover, 1.3 NO _x , 0.4 SO ₂ 31k
10:23	9	1000			Smoke ahead ~ 6 Runways (Cunard)
10:26	9	1000	70	Ramsgate	2.1 NO _x , 0.5 SO ₂ , 10 O ₃ , 100 CO 20k
10:28	9	1000			6 NO _x , 2 SO ₂ , 55k
10:31	19	1000	8°		12 NO _x , 3 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 122 CO 20k
10:37	19	1000	355	Sizewell	1.4 NO _x , 0.4 SO ₂ , 10 O ₃ , 20k
10:39	19	1000	355	"	12 0.6 10 95 CO 40k
10:43	19	1000	1°	Lowestoft	Lowestoft 1 NO _x , 0.3 SO ₂ , 20k
10:48	19	1060	343	G-Y	Wind farm 1 NO _x , 0.8 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 98 CO 40k
10:52	19	1000	307	Sea Palling	1.2 NO _x , 0.7 SO ₂ , 10 O ₃ , 93 CO 18k
10:55	19	1100	291	Blickling	2 sm ^s 3 pm ₁₀ 150, 70, 96 CO 33k
11:00	19	1020	325	87	1.8 NO _x , 0.7 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 95 CO 25k
11:02	19	1000	325	Seagulls	RAF flying circle + tornadoes
11:04	19	1000	326	S-Hills	more tornadoes 1.9 NO _x , 0.3 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 96 CO
11:06	19	1000	"	Humber	1.9 NO _x , 0.3 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃
11:08	19	1000	326	Humber	5 NO _x , 2 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 94 CO 15k
11:11	19	1000	326	Humber	1000ft ship's mast 3 pm ₁₀ NO _x , 2 SO ₂ , 48k
11:14	19	1000	326	Spur	6 pm ₁₀ NO _x , 2 SO ₂ , 9 O ₃ , 113 CO 54k
11:16	19	1000	325	2-Turns	8... 2... 8... 104... 20k

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.112**

 Date **19 July**

 Page **3** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc).
11:17	10	1000	326		17NO, 4SO, 7O ₂ 10300 51k
11:20	10	1000	326	FLAMPAS	2.6NO, 0.5SO, 80, 9510, 58k
11:22	10	1000	312	80	WP point 80, 0.8NO, 0.2SO, 11.3
11:26	10	1020	314	Fulgencis	0.4NO, 0.1SO, 90, 9000, 35k
11:29	10	1020	316	"	0 " 0 " 10' 22000ft
11:32	10	1000	315	Whitby	Remains in clear 5910 32k
11:33	10	1000	315	Teeside	NOx bsp 250, 80, 11400 60k
11:33	10	1000	313	Thames	" 0.7, 0.3SO, 100, 9100 50k
11:30	10	1020	335		WP 70, 0.7NO, 0.3SO, 90, 9150
11:41	10	1030	330	Newcastle	NO 0.2, 0.2SO, 100, 9910 14k
11:45	10	1000	337	Morpeth	NO, 0.5, 50, 0.07, 100, 8800 9k
11:51	10	1020	335	FAEN	" 0.3, " 0.2, 100, 8800 6k
11:56	10	1000	318	WP 77	WP 77
11:57	10	1000	319	Berwick	NO 0.2, SO 0.1, 110, 9200 21k
12:01	10	1020	319	"	NO 1.1, SO 1.1, 90, 9900 40k
12:02	10	1000	320	St Abb's	" 1.5, SO 0.5, 90, 9700 36
12:05	10	1000	320	"	0.2 0.2 100 92 140k
12:06	9	1000	320	DUNBAR	Circle Run 9
12:08	-	↓	180		turning around descending to 2500f
12:08	10	250	180		
12:09	P6	↑	180		End of run profile: 5000f
12:10	11	500	183		Run at 500f
12:11	P7	1000	161		
12:12	12	1000	152		Run 12 at 1000f
12:12	P8	↑	152	St Abb's	profile to 2000f
12:13	13	2000	152	Morpeth	
12:14	P9	↑	152	"	profile to 4000f
12:16	14	4000	152	St Abb's	Run to 4000f (WP 77)
12:17	P10	↑			profile to 6000f

(1 ms)
 Rain
 upwind
 white
 noise

Mission Scientist's Log

DANN FORSTER

Flight No B.112.

Date ... 19 JULY '05

Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc).
11:19	15	6000	171		
11:22	15	6000	171		-0.7 NO _x , 0.17 SO ₂ , 30 CO ₂ , 91 CO, 32k
11:27	15	6000	171		-0.4, 0.3, 27 88 4k
12:34	15	↓	346		Concurrently, clear descent to 1000ft
12:35	15	↓			turning with track south
12:37			189	Newcastle	Rain ahead. Zero NO _x , SO ₂
12:38	16	1000	189	Dunoon	New run Rain " " 32k
12:40	16	1000	170	"	NO _x 0.3, SO ₂ 0.3, O ₃ 12, CO 91
12:43	16	1000	148	WSP79	NO _x 0.4, SO ₂ 0.3, NO ₂ 91 CO 32k
12:47	16	1000	146	Whithy	6 NO _x , 4 SO ₂ , 100, 101 CO, 40k
12:49	16	1000	161	"	Chlorophyll, 0.1 NO _x , 0.1 SO ₂ , 112 CO
12:52	16	1000	145	Scarbrough	NO _x 0.3, SO ₂ 0.1, O ₃ 12, CO 92, 24k
12:59	16	1000	161	WSP80	NO _x 0.6, SO ₂ 0.3, O ₃ 10, CO 94 36k
13:01	16	1000	160	WSP82	1.4, 0.3, O ₃ 8, 97 32k
13:02	16	1000	160	"	1.5, 0.4, 7
13:03	16	1000	160	Spurn Pt	2.0, 0.6, 8, 102 45k
13:05	16	1000	161	Spurn Pt	5, 2, 9, 180 20k
13:06	16	1000	160	Humbly	5, 2, 9, 98 25k
13:10	16	1000	160	Lincs	2, 0.8, 10
13:12	16	1000	160	"	1.3, 0.3, 11, 93 30k
13:14	16	1000	160	Lincs	0.7, 0.3, 12, 93 32k
13:17	16	1000	160	Lincs	1.3, 0.4, 11, 104 42k
13:18	16	1000	135	Newcastle	2.2, 0.7, 11, 96 36k
13:20	16	1000	135	87	1.5, 0.9, 11, 92 46k
13:22	16	1000	114	Newcastle	0.8, 0.7, 11, 93 48k
13:24	16	1000	133	"	
13:25	16	1000	133	"	1.4, 0.4, 12, 95 41k
13:26	End 16				Filters stop, Baffles run stop
13:28	17	10000	261	Newcastle	Some BAC ₁ samples at 10k into BAC ₂
13:32	17	10k	262	"	NO _x 0.6, SO ₂ 0.7, CO 46, CO ₂ 95, 48k

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B112

Date : 19/7/05

Operator and contact info : Ruth Purvis (rupu@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	CEH instrument
TDLAS	None
WAS	N/A

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cals) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
8:38	On ground	Cal gas low
9:11	FL100	
9:46	1000ft	
10:16	1000ft	
10:44	1000ft	
11:26	1000ft	
12:43	1000ft	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B112

Date: 19 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 1 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:02			60	Not fitted							T/o Cranfield
09:05:37											Run 1 fl100 (cals) started
09:10:00	25	0.08	60		0	0		0.007	0		
09:15:00	22	0.07	60		0	0		0	0		
09:28:00	45	0.07	60		0	0		0	0		Run 2 fl60
09:30:00	208	0.08	60		0	0		0	0		P1 5000
09:31:30	391	0	60		0	0		0	0		R3 4000
09:34	465	0.08	60		0	0		0	0		R4 2000
09:37	1344	0.06	60		0	0		0	0		R5 1000
09:31	309	0.08	60		0	0		0	0		R6 500
09:41	294	0.08	60		0	0		0	0		R7 250
09:43	333	0.08	60		0	0		0	0		R8 1000
09:45											
09:50											FSSP computer restarted Data suspect
10:00	223	0.08	0		0	0		0	0		R8 1000
10:13:30	155	0.08	0		0	0		0	0		R9 1000 wp43
10:15:30	308	0.07	0		0	0		0	0		
10:19:30	215	0.08									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Page 2 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:21:30	267	0.08	0	Not fitted	0	0		0	0		R9 1000 wp 42
10:23:30	300	0.08									
10:25:30	214	0.08									
10:27:30	216	0.09									
10:29:30	280	0.08									
10:31:30	278	0.08									
10:33:30	265	0.08									
10:35:30	220	0.08									
10:37:30	258	0.07									
10:39:30	368	0.08									
10:41:30	254	0.08									
10:44:00	259	0.08									
10:46:00	272	0.08									
10:48:00	159	0.07									
10:50:00	239	0.07									
10:52:00	195	0.07									
10:54:00	337	0.08									
10:56:00	335	0.08									
10:58:00	207	0.08									
11:00:00	186	0.08									
11:02:00	185	0.08									
11:04:00	266	0.08									
11:06:00	313	0.08									
11:08:00	306	0.09									
11:10:00	225	0.09									
11:12:00	368	0.09									
11:14:00	204	0.08									
11:16:00	369	0.09									
11:18:00	223	0.09									
11:20:00	181	0.09									
11:22:00	234	0.07									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B112

Date: 19 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:24:00	207	0.07									
11:26:00	168	0.08									
11:28:00	98	0.08									
11:30:00	100	0.09									
11:32:00	111	0.08									
11:34:00	94	0.08									
11:36:00	128	0.09									
11:40:00	136	0.15									
11:42:00	128	0.1									
11:44:00	217	0.08									
11:46:00	150	0.09									
11:48:00	197	0.07									
11:50:00	84	0.08									
11:52:00	83	0.08									
11:54:00	99	0.09									
11:56:00	115	0.08									
11:58:00	143	0.07									
12:00:00	126	0.07									
12:02:00	130	0.07									
12:04:00	97	0.09									
12:06:00	140	0.07									End of run 9
12:09:00	72	0.12									R10 250
12:10:20	84	0.09									R11 500
12:12:00	53	0.07									R12 1000
12:14:00	76	0.1									R13 2000
12:15:45	115	0.08									P9 3000

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B112

Date: 19 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:17:00	151	0.07									R14 4000
12:18:42	25	0.09									P10 fl50
12:20:00	75	0.06									R15 6000
12:25:00	23	0.08									
12:27:00											Fssp reset
											On 'link' fssp fifo go to enabled for 1second then return to reset. Block transfers, total stobe counts and strobe counts do not update.
12:38:00											R16 208 1000
12:40:00	216	0.27	???								
12:42:00	194	0.08									
											Recycled power to fssp probe. Fifos now stay enabled
12:47:00	180	0.09									
12:49:00	190	0.09									
12:51:00	142	0.08									
12:53:00	168	0.08									
12:55:00	215	0.08									
12:57:00	177	0.09									
12:59:00	136	0.08									

Flight No. B112

Route

Date 19/7/2005

Take Off 0900 GMT

Bag Samplers: A. McWALD M. THEOBALD

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
132	09:09:30	09:10:00	52.5N	0.2 E	10000 ft
557	09:11:00	09:11:30			10000 ft
080	09:12:00	09:12:30			"
010	09:13:00	09:13:30			"
501	09:14:00	09:14:30			"
613	09:15:00	09:15:30	52.6N	0.7 E	"
459	09:16:00	09:16:30			"
285	09:17:00	09:17:30			"
238	09:18:00	09:18:30			"
170	09:19:00	09:19:30	52.6N	1.1 E	"
060	09:28:05	09:28:35	52.3N	1.8 E	6000ft
260	09:29:20	09:29:50			6000 - 5200ft
518	09:31:10	09:31:40			4000ft
339	09:32:20	09:32:50			4000 - 3500ft
004	09:34:10	09:34:40			2000ft
436	09:35:35	09:36:05			2000 - 1500ft
320	09:36:55	09:37:25			1000ft
078	09:39:00	09:39:30			500ft
407	09:40:42	09:41:12	51.6N	1.6 E	250ft
508	09:42:00	09:43:30			1000ft
650	09:44:00	09:44:30			
658	09:45:00	09:45:30			
024	09:46:00	09:46:50			
389	09:47:00	09:47:30	51.3N	1.5 E	
022	09:48:00	09:48:30			
119	09:49:00	09:49:30			
382	09:50:00	09:50:30			
545	09:52:00	09:52:30			
073	09:53:00	09:53:30			
652	09:54:00	09:54:30			
213	09:55:00	09:55:30	50.9N	1.2 E	
145	09:56:00	09:56:30			
502	09:57:00	09:57:30			
122	09:58:00	09:58:30			
233	09:59:00	09:59:30			
394	10:00:00	10:00:30			
546	10:01:00	10:01:30	50.8N	0.8 E	
484	10:02:00	10:02:30			
392	10:03:00	10:03:30			
458	10:04:00	10:04:30			
482	10:05:00	10:05:30			

BACKGROUND

← correct height (2250) ft

← BAG 209

09:51:00
09:51:30
209 →

Flight No. B112Route Date 19/07/2005Take Off 0900 GMTBag Samplers: A McDONALD M. THEOBALDSheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
387	10:06:00	10:06:30	50.6N	0.9E	LAST BAG OF RUN
282	10:07:10	10:07:40			1000 - 4000 ft
388	10:08:00	10:08:30			4000 - 5000 ft
335?	10:11:00	10:11:30			4500 - 3800 ft
473	10:12:00	10:12:30			3000 - 1400 ft
396	10:13:00	10:13:30			1200 - 1000 ft
330	10:14:00	10:14:30			1000 ft
384	10:15:00	10:15:30			
381	10:16:00	10:16:30	50.9N	1.1E	
385	10:17:00	10:17:30			
225	10:18:00	10:18:30			
408	10:19:00	10:19:30			
204	10:20:00	10:20:30			WAYPOINT 42
543	10:21:00	10:21:30			
383	10:22:00	10:22:30	51.1N	1.5E	
898	10:23:00	10:23:30			
400	10:24:00	10:24:30			
505	10:25:00	10:25:30			
409	10:26:00	10:26:30			
211	10:27:00	10:27:30			
527	10:28:00	10:28:30	51.5N	1.6E	
220	10:29:00	10:29:30			
529	10:30:00	10:30:30			
234	10:31:00	10:31:30			
488	10:32:00	10:32:30			
269	10:33:00	10:33:30			
386	10:34:06	10:34:36	51.8N	1.7E	
399	10:35:08	10:35:38			WAYPOINT 41
397	10:36:00	10:36:30			
390	10:37:00	10:37:30			
202	10:38:00	10:38:30			
509	10:39:00	10:39:30			
460	10:40:00	10:40:30	52.2N	1.7E	
474	10:41:00	10:41:30			
548	10:42:00	10:42:30			
391	10:43:00	10:43:30			
475	10:44:00	10:44:30			
090	10:45:00	10:45:30			
487	10:46:00	10:46:30	52.5N	1.7E	
028	10:47:00	10:47:30			
363	10:48:00	10:48:30			

RUN START

Flight No. Route Date Take Off GMTBag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
184	10:49:00	10:49:30			1000 ft
177	10:50:00	10:50:30			
077	10:51:00	10:51:30			
485	10:52:00	10:52:30			
470	10:53:00	10:53:30			
270	10:54:00	10:54:30	52.9N	1.3E	
210	10:55:00	10:55:30			35% SAMPLE
265	10:56:03	10:56:33			1000 ft
263	10:57:00	10:57:30			
312	10:58:00	10:58:30			
503	10:59:06	10:59:36			
231	10:00:00	11:00:30			
329	01:00	01:30			
311	02:00	02:30			
426	03:00	03:30			
532	04:00	04:30			
507	05:00	05:30			
267	06:00	06:30			
223	07:00	07:30			
230	08:00	08:30			
327	09:00	09:30			
522	10:00	10:30			
332	11:00	11:30			
206	12:00	12:30			
218	13:00	13:30			
205	14:00	14:30			
526	15:00	15:30			
226	16:00	16:30			
331	17:00	17:30			
544	18:00	18:30			
510	19:00	19:30	54.0N	0.1E	
079	20:00	20:30			
651	21:00	21:30			WAYPOINT 80
378	22:00	22:30			1000 ft
333	23:00	23:30			
268	24:06	24:36			
288	25:00	25:30			
236	26:00	26:30			
237	27:00	27:30			
533	28:00	28:30			
235	29:00	29:30	54.4N	0.3W	

Flight No. B112Route Date 19/10/2005Take Off 0900 GMTBag Samplers: A. McDONNELL, M. THEOBALDSheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
426	11:30:00	11:30:30			1000ft
338	11:31:00	11:31:30			
215	32:00	32:30			
217	33:00	33:30			
486	34:00	34:30			
528	35:00	35:30	54.7N	0.7W	
219	36:00	36:30			
540	37:00	37:30			
542	38:00	38:30			
340	39:00	39:30			WAYPOINT 79
262	40:00	40:30			1000ft
477	41:00	41:30			
208	42:00	42:30	55.0N	1.0W	
393	43:00	43:30			
321	44:00	44:30			
261	45:00	45:30			
461	46:00	46:30			
472	47:00	47:30			
166	48:00	48:30	55.3N	1.2W	
478	49:00	49:30			
559	50:00	50:30			
428	51:00	51:30			
525	52:00	52:30			
124	53:10	53:40			
016	54:00	54:30			
190	55:00	55:30			
049	56:00	56:30			
168	57:00	57:30			
174	58:00	58:30	55.8N	1.6W	
339	59:00	59:30			
147	12:00:00	12:00:30			
149	01:00	01:30			
455	02:00	02:30			
141	03:00	03:30			
163	04:00	04:30			WAYPOINT 76
450	05:00	05:30			LAST BAG OF RUN 9
142	06:00	06:30			
378	07:00	07:30			
164	08:50	09:20			250 ft
506	10:10	10:40			500 ft
379	11:50	12:20			1000 ft

Flight No. B112

Route

Date 19/07/2005

Take Off 0900 GMT

Bag Samplers: A. McDONALD, M. THEBALD

Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
485	12:13:50	12:14:20			2000 ft
326	12:15:10	12:15:40			2000 - 3000ft
143	12:16:55	12:17:25			6000ft
085	12:18:20	12:18:50			5000 - 6000ft
376	12:19:45	12:20:15			6000ft
TOTL ET BREAK AT 6000 FT					
471	12:40:00	12:40:30			1,000 ft
490	41:00	41:30			
207	42:00	42:30			
068	43:00	43:30	54.8N	0.8W	
212	44:00	44:30			
336	45:00	45:30			
395	46:00	46:30			
833 337	47:00	47:30			
216	48:00	48:30			
201	49:00	49:30			
264	50:00	50:30			
146	51:00	51:30			
334	52:00	52:30			
530	53:00	53:30			
504	54:00	54:30			
266	55:00	55:30	54.2N	0.0E	
323	56:00	56:30			
481	57:00	57:30			
322	58:00	58:30			
452	59:00	59:30			
349	13:00:00	13:00:30			
081	01:00	01:30			
076	02:00	02:30			
179	02:00				
242	04:00	04:30			
187	05:00	05:30			
018	06:00	06:30			
029	07:00	07:30			
042	08:00	08:30			
025	09:00	09:30			
063	10:00	10:30			
088	11:00	11:30			
421	12:00	12:30			
254	13:00	13:30			
464	13:14:00	13:14:30			

→ IGNORE; MARK DISTRACTED BY PLUME

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B111
Date: 14/07/2005

Campaign Name: AMPEP
Operator: M. Neilsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
9:07:42	9:08:29	16	Run 2 at 6000 ft	3.20
09:09:31	9:10:16	17	In profile	3.27
09:10:34	9:11:19	18	Run 3 at 4000 ft	3.27
09:13:36	9:14:21	19	Run 4 at 2000 ft	3.34
09:15:50	9:16:30	20	Run 5 at 1000 ft	3.34
09:18:27	9:19:07	21	Run 6 at 100 ft	3.36
09:21:35	9:22:35	22	Run 7	3.35
09:31:28	9:32:28	23	Run 8 at 1000 ft	3.36
09:44:18	9:45:18	24	Run 8 at 1000 ft	3.36
09:48:26	9:48:56	25	Run 8 at 1000 ft high Sulphur	3.33
09:49:08	9:49:39	26	Teeside	3.33
09:59:36	10:00:06	27	High NOxy, peak on sulphur	3.30
10:00:22	10:00:52	28	High NOxy, peak on sulphur	3.33
10:10:07	10:10:37	29		3.34
10:19:37	10:20:07	30	Downwind from Edinburgh	3.34
10:34:06	10:34:36	31		3.34
10:39:47	10:40:17	32	High organics from AMS	3.33
10:45:53	10:46:33	49	Run 9 (100 ft)	3.36
10:47:17	10:47:57	50	Run 10 (500 ft)	3.35
10:48:54	10:49:34	51	Run 11 (1000 ft)	3.35
10:50:44	10:51:24	52	Part Run 12	3.34
10:56:46	10:57:26	53	Run 14 (6000 ft)	3.34
11:15:43	11:16:23	54	Run 16 high NOxy (zero AMS)- same plume as caught on way up?	3.35
11:17:27	11:18:07	55	Core chemistry indicates pollution	3.34
11:27:58	11:28:38	56		3.36

11:41:03	11:41:43	57	1000 ft	3.35
11:43:51	11:44:31	58	High CO (up to 1 ppm)	3.35
11:44:37	11:45:07	59	High CO (up to 1 ppm)	3.35
12:00:15	12:00:45	60	High NOx (ppb)	3.10
12:03:18	12:03:48	61	High NO2 (14 ppb); High CO (~200)	3.00
12:15:02	12:015:32	62		3.30
12:32:15	12:32:46	63	Plume? (Possibly London plume)	3.30
12:34:57	12:35:27	64	NOxy levels lower but CO rising	3.34

DATE: 19/07/05

FLIGHT: B112 AMPER

OPERATOR: ICNB

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS, Grimm CPC logging	Software will log on EP folder to London - Antibio			
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet - on EP folder → London Antibio			
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓	Port 2	
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓	checked mass range first	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓		Check gain at current V
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, mz selection, left click on row	✓		15,16,17,30,46*
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		wait
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, mz selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓		Check tof windows
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓		SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		No		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, mz selection, left click on row	X		14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	X		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, mz selection, left click on row	X		
General alteration, 10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	X		Check tof windows	
Close inlet		✓			
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop		✓		
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER
Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
ShutDown	Turn off Multiplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box	✓		
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack	✓		
	Turn off heater, chopper, the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

NB SMPS Sample Volume = 0.42 don't believe it - set sheet at 4.2

measured sample flow = 0.42 as expected.

DATE: 19/07/05 FLIGHT: B112 AMPER OPERATOR: KWB

Time	Event
11:21:05	Turning J report WP (60)
11:34:32	Turning - show WP (77) Clean
	Dakota Penton - Edinburgh - for NAME for CLIPAP
11:55:12	WP (77) turning for (76)
12:04:15	Through end (76) 302, NOx plume CAC too PCASO noise
12:05:32	end filter - background levels (R1 end) - descending to 250'
12:08:46	✓ R10 start @ 750'
12:09:42	end R10 start P6 to 500'
12:10:09	end P6 start R11 at 500'
12:11:03	end R11 start P7 to
12:11:43	end P7 start R12 at 1000'
12:12:33	end R12 start P8 to 2000'
12:13:43	end P8 start R13 at 2800'
12:14:47	end R13 start P9 to 4000'
12:16:49	end P9 start R14 at 4000' just past WP (77)
12:17:42	end R14 start P10 to 6000'
12:17:56	end P10 start R15 at 6000'
12:20:40	end R15 t/break
12:37:37	start R16 1000' (77) ↔ (79) 4 miles to go - Zero Particle Filter run at 12:38
12:42:53	at WP (79) → WP (60)
12:48:00	break on filter - just at end of plume
12:58:39	WP (60) turning for WP (67)
13:02:35	NOx plume - MSci - going into plume again - Not much on AMS SO2 increase only - CO delayed increase + 180
13:12:00	still high SO2, O3, NH4 O3 → 1.23 SO2.
13:25:00	end R16 at 1000' - climbing for NOxy Cal
13:28:41	10000' NOxy cal. seen 17 - Will continue at 10000' - then continue by ZP filter into landing (NOxy cal done) stopped logging - put filter into inlet (CAC still in airway -) AMS into logging
13:50:00	stopped AMS
13:40:05	logging gen alt work - ZP filter - CAC on labrow
13:41:04	NOxy cal done -
	landed 2:54:36 on BST
14:04	Stopped logging - set logging to manual

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 19/10/05 FLIGHT: B112 AMDEF OPERATOR: KNS

actually need MS range at earlier than in check list
 ↓
 AS ↑ ms 2.1 instead

Tuning

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	24	28	22
Def Outer	14	16	11
Heater Bias	-6.52	-6.69	-6.5
Focus	15.50	15.00	12.5
Extraction	242	204	220

-18% not accepted

double peak

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner		28	22
Def Outer		16	11
Heater Bias		-6.69	-6.5
Focus		15.50	12.5
Extraction		200	220

-5% - accept - change extraction back to 242

MS 1.87 → 1.8 MHz
 TOF 1.53 → 1.5 MHz

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
 This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.5	n/a
KV Change	0	0.025kV
Gain	3.65	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.15	1

Not accepted

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0	0.025kV
Gain	3.25	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.02	1

-0.025!

Ionization Efficiency Cal

pre flight

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.278×10^{-6}	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)		4
IPP NO3	297.06	400
IPP NH4	405.11	550
Airbeam MS	2.25 MHz	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.41 MHz	2.00E+06
Run Number	2070	n/a

very low (checked up in flight) →

IE/AB 5 5.75×10^{-3}
 New/cht 0.62 mblach

Filter Run

TIME:	
Run number	

in flight

post flight

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.836×10^{-6}	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3372	4
IPP NO3	431.40	400
IPP NH4	449.84	550
Airbeam MS	2.24×10^4	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.84×10^6	2.00E+06
Run Number	2022	n/a

TIME:	
Run number	

N/A

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 19/10/05

FLIGHT: B112 AMPCP

OPERATOR: KNB

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	N/A		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300 (AGAIN!)	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	F=1.9 AB ₂₈ =1.88/1.65
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	no gas
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	recheck gain, MV a bit
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal <i>move much higher</i>	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	TOF MS rubbish! 1.45
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	MS is 2.10 ?
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM <i>short inlet</i>	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan <i>200</i>	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	+28
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMS\AMSCODE\AMSMMenu.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
	Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓		
	Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓		
	General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓		

Need MS check earlier
ADJUST FILAMENT →
I TO GET
INCREASE IN
OF 100%

CALIBRATION
DUMP
SECTIONS →

to what? →

MR V

NB - sample flow: 0.6l - rubbish - set sheath = 4.2 lpm - NO₂ in correct window of TOF screen

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 19/10/05

FLIGHT: B112 AMFEP

OPERATOR: K.N.B.

Time: 6:02	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓		
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓		
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓		
	Turn on: Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓		
	Turn on Alcatel... 100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓	Monitor Pump Currents	
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
Turbo pump 6 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓			
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓		Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓		
	Turn on Copper <i>Oh yes: pretty nice!!!</i>	Electronics box	✓		Approx 125Hz
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓		
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓		
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		NEGATIVE NUMBER
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓		
Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			

ADD:
CHECK
COOLING
FANS ARE
OK →
IN TPs 3, 4
(and 2) + ALI

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 19/07/08 FLIGHT: B112 AMPEO OPERATOR: KNS

Time 13:07

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.27	0.86	96.4	98
2	3.40	3.5	100.5	100
3	1.35	1	100.6	100
4	0.62	0.5	100.5	100
5	0.41	0.4	100.2	100
6	0.43	0.46	100.2	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.83	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	581.5	580
Heater B	72.9	75V
Multiplier	2.476	n/a
Pressure	1.818	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1.0	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.39	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.93	2Mhz
Flow	2.022	2

Chopin 1.35-0 Hz

Flu/Flon 1.815/-

1000'

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B112**

Date: 19/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	y	N
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	Y
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B112

Date: 19/07/05

Instruments

1. SATCOM-C queued but mostly failed to send messages.
2. Some problems re zeros on Nitric acid channel
3. FFSSP PC needed rebooting twice
4. SID2 not operational

Aircraft

